

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Deliverable D8.4

Version N°1.3

Grant Agreement	101103706
Project website	https://battereverse.eu
Contractual deadline	31/10/2023 (M6)*
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Nature	Deliverable
Author	CEA
Contributors	ALL
Reviewers	WP leaders, PCo M. Chami (CEA)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement n°101103706. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Change Log

Version	Description of change
V1.0	First version of the DMP
V1.1	Contributions from Frontier (Kostas Christidis)
V1.2	First delivered version (M7) : WP leaders review
V1.3	PCo review and validation

CTREG/23-041

*For the D8.4 deliverable, one month delay requested to the PO, accepted the 26th of October 2023 (new due date : 30th November 2023):

The screenshot shows the 'RESEARCH & INNOVATION Grant Management Services' interface. It features a navigation bar with 'Grant Management Services' and a user profile for 'Marianne Chami'. Below the navigation bar is a 'Communication Centre' section. A message from the Coordinator (Chami, Marianne) to the Project Officer (Bernardo Luis) is displayed, dated 22 Oct. The message content is as follows:

3 demands concerning the project New reply

Dear Project Officer Bernardo Luis,

3 : One month delay demand, for the deliverable D8.4 (Data management plan)

The D8.4 deliverable is in progress, we kindly ask one additional month fo finalize the Word document.

No risk identified for the project

No impact identified for the project

26 Oct

Dear Marianne,

The one month delay is fine by me

Regards

Bernardo

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Introduction

This document is the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the BatteReverse project. It aims to describe the data collected, produced or reused during the project. It covers the whole data lifecycle, including storage, management, and possible reuse by third parties after the project's end.

It also describes how the project's partners intend to fulfil expectations related to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles for research data.

This deliverable is based on the DMP template¹ provided by the European Commission and will be revised during the project lifecycle. Each project's partner using or producing data will update the document as soon as new or more accurate information concerning data appears in work packages.

This document is public (released under CC BY² license) and will be stored on Zenodo³ public repository.

1. Data summary

BatteReverse main objective is to enable the next generation of battery reverse logistics (RL). The project developments cover a wide variety of physical and digital tools such as safety packaging, automated dismantling and sorting, acoustic testing, battery module diagnosis and remaining useful life fast assessment. This variety rationally suggests a need for various datasets related to battery modules and usages.

1.1. Purpose of data within the project

BatteReverse uses and generates battery data from several sources in order to fulfil its development objectives:

- Battery metadata: various information (identifier, origin ...) related to battery and modules traceability within the project shall be collected from partners providing the tested modules (car manufacturers). Aside from traceability purposes, some technical specifications are also required in order to ensure correct handling, safe dismantling, and cycling measure operations. This also relates to the battery passport initiative addressed in WP2.
- Battery usage history: the possibility to get access to subsets of battery usage history for the need of specific tasks will be clarified in a future version of this document.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

² <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

- Experimental measures: a large part of data created in the project concerns physical measures of battery module. The diagnostics and sorting tools will require these data, both for development purpose and for validation stages.
- Battery usage profiles: a set of second life profiles must be defined. The sorting tool development requires such profiles for module testing, taking into account the future second life usage characteristics.

Batterreverse might consider the usage of open source data to augment partner data, though no specific case is yet identified. Batterreverse may also technically rely on various open source implementations of data analysis or machine learning techniques.

BatteReverse does not make use of personal data.

A project repository has been setup and made available to all project’s partners. Data generated and collected will generally be stored on this repository. Data with restricted access, or requiring a robust versioning solution, are managed separately (on partner’s data storage facilities).

1.2. Dataset inventory table

Each work package leader gathers information about data generated in the project and adds the datasets metadata in a common dataset inventory table. This table is located on the project repository⁴. This table provides a convenient way of managing day-to-day evolution in each work package concerning generated data.

DATA_REF_ID (WP-TASK_ID)		GENERAL METADATA						
WP-TASK	ID	NAME	LEAD PROVIDER	OTHER PROVIDERS	TYPE	FORMAT	DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE IN THE PROJECT	REPOSITORY
8.3	D8.4	Data Management Plan (DMP)	CEA	ALL	DOC	docx, pdf	Batterreverse Data Management Plan	BatteReverse repository + zenodo

Figure 1 Datasets metadata table (1)

DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE IN THE PROJECT	REPOSITORY	DATA ACCESSIBILITY			EXISTING DATA REUSE			
		ACCESSIBILITY	ACCESSIBILITY LICENSE	DATA USERS	RELATED PUBLICATION	REUSED	REUSED DATA SOURCE	REUSED DATA LICENSE
Batterreverse Data Management Plan	BatteReverse repository + zenodo	G	CC BY	ALL	-	YES	EC DMP recommended template	Not relevant

Figure 2 Datasets metadata table (2)

The above figures show the expected metadata for each datasets. It falls into four main sections.

⁴

https://batterreverse.cea.fr/WP8%20Documents/Deliverables%20WP8%20preparation/batterreverse_dataset_inventory_table.xlsx?Web=1 (latest version)

1.2.1. Dataset reference

Each dataset shall be identified by a unique reference within the project. The DATA_REF_ID field addresses this need. It is composed with the aggregation of the project's work package and task numbers where the dataset comes from, and an additional id to distinguish dataset from the same task. As an example, the "Data Management Plan (DMP)" deliverable document produced in task 8.3 is registered under the "8.3_D8.4" DATA_REF_ID.

1.2.2. General metadata

This section groups several basic fields: NAME, LEAD PROVIDER, OTHER PROVIDERS, TYPE, FORMAT, DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE IN THE PROJECT, and REPOSITORY.

The LEAD PROVIDER indicates the organization that provides the data, and which takes the responsibility for this data within the project. The lead provider also indicates the accessibility status of the dataset. Other organizations may contribute to the dataset (listed in OTHER PROVIDERS). As the accessibility concerns every provider (and users), a separate dataset reference is required as soon as different providers have different views concerning data accessibility.

The TYPE field gives a hint on the data nature, DATA or DOC with optionally more detailed information (image, text, list of measures...) provided in the table. The FORMAT field completes the TYPE with data language, ontological description, or file format specification (ex: pdf, csv, domain language specification...).

The next field, DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE IN THE PROJECT, contains any information that helps in understanding what the dataset is, and how it is used in the project. A short description about how data is collected can also be added here.

The repository field contains the location where the dataset is stored. The BatteReverse collaborative platform can host datasets that are accessible to every partner in the project. Other access policies will require different strategies described in this field. Some specific kinds of data may also require specific kinds of storage with versioning support (ex: dedicated source version control system for code development...).

1.2.3. Data accessibility

Each lead data provider also defines the accessibility for data it provides. The following policies are defined:

- *[G] General public access*: data is shared for public use, which generally means that it is stored on an existing public access server.
- *[S] Scientific community access*: data is used or referenced in scientific communication like conference or publication. Data is not communicated as-is outside BattReverse but may be presented to an external audience (figures, graphs...).
- *[P] Project partners*: data is available for use in BatteReverse by project partners only.

- *[R] Restricted project partners*: data is available by a restricted list of partners that need the data to achieve their task in the project only.
- *[I] Internal use*: the lead provider creates data for his own internal use.

Note that “*General public*” access does not implies free or fully open public reuse: the lead provider defines the applicable licence in the ACCESSIBILITY LICENCE field. The field content is a link to the document containing specific licence terms established by data providers, or any well-established licence (ex: LGPL, MIT, open creative common licence...). Such reusable links towards legal licence document may be listed in the “table usage” tab (e.g.: “CC BY” refers to <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>).

WP USERS column contains the list of BatteReverse work packages that need data access to achieve their respective tasks.

DATA USERS field contains the list of BatteReverse partners that intend to use data for the only purpose of their work in the project. In case the accessibility is stated *[I]internal use* or *[R]restricted list of BatteReverse partners* a specific request to the lead provider is required to explicitly ask for data access.

BatteReverse foresees several publications of project research work. The RELATED PUBLICATION keeps track between the publication and dataset it refers. The field contains a list of the related publications id. The list of project publications is given in a side tab (from the same excel document as the inventory table). The publication id is made of “PUBLI” identifying prefix, number of work package proposing the publication, a publication numbering for uniqueness of the identifier, ex: PUBLI.5.01 relates to the WP5 “Fast diagnosis method for sorting 2nd life battery module”.

1.2.4. Existing data reuse

Whenever existing data produced outside the project is reused in BatteReverse, it must be identified as such in the dataset inventory table. In that case, the lead provider is the BatteReverse partner that needs and uses the data.

REUSE DATA SOURCE contains the origin of the reused data (may be a link towards data or location where one can retrieve it).

REUSED DATA LICENSE shall explicit under which conditions the data may be reused (name of the licence or link to data licence page). The lead provider ensures the licence terms are compliant to the use of the existing data in the project.

1.3. Other relevant deliverables and documents

The following deliverables contain relevant information about data management:

- BatteReverse Grant Agreement

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- D1.1 – Technical development plan
- D2.2 – Prototype of the battery data model
- D2.3 – Data access policies for battery passport
- D2.4 - Integrated Battery Data Space platform prototype

2. FAIR data

BatteReverse will make its best to ensure FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management in accordance with the grant agreement⁵ and the consortium agreement⁶ of the project. Obviously, some of the datasets generated or collected in the project cannot be shared for industrial competition reasons, or ongoing research opportunities protection.

2.1. Making data Findable

The data inventory table helps dealing with data internal management in BatteReverse. This table gathers metadata and reference for all data in the project. This detailed metadata table is not exposed outside the project.

Concerning the project's datasets defined as public ([G] - *General public access*) a deposit on an open repository is expected, Zenodo⁷ is the repository selected for this in BattereReverse. This will be further specified in the project communication and dissemination task (T7.2) in order to ensure the use of homogeneous project related metadata (required metadata: project name, grant agreement number, common attachment group, other information...). The lead provider will choose relevant keywords for public datasets description.

2.2. Making data Accessible

Zenodo creates a unique DOI (data object identifier) for each stored data, in case another public repository service is used, the lead provider will make sure a DOI is created for public datasets.

Non-public datasets can be stored on BatteReverse collaborative platform (secured individual access support), or organization specific internal repositories. In the context of the Data Space in WP2, secure and trusted access to parts of the datasets will be provided to members of the BatteReverse consortium. The BatteReverse collaborative platform will remain available several months after the end of the project. The long-term storage strategy is not yet defined in current version of the DMP.

⁵ [https://battereReverse.cea.fr/Governance/Grant%20Agreement%20-%20GAP-101103706%20\(3\).pdf?Web=1](https://battereReverse.cea.fr/Governance/Grant%20Agreement%20-%20GAP-101103706%20(3).pdf?Web=1)

⁶ https://battereReverse.cea.fr/Governance/DESCA_CA_BATTEREVERSE_VF.pdf?Web=1

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

The project defines several levels of data accessibility from “General public access” to “Internal use only”. When datasets are expected to be accessible outside the project, a licence is provided that describes usage terms and conditions. The chosen standard licence (or organization specific licence) is specified in the common inventory table.

BatteReverse will not provide standardized access protocols for all available data. However, in the context of the Data Space (WP2), parts of the datasets will become available inside the consortium in a standardised IDSA-compliant way, requiring bilateral access agreements and data access policies.

2.3. Making data Interoperable

To increase the interoperability of our data, we will use widely accepted vocabularies across datasets for both data and metadata. Tables will provide dataset information including a general overview, detailed content, technical descriptions, and access information. Given that most of the project's sharable data will be either text-based or numeric, common formats like JSON and CSV will be used allowing seamless usage by other researchers through open-source tools. If there is a need to use customized data formats during the project, we will establish and document specific sharing mechanisms to maintain accessibility.

BatteReverse will also develop a battery data model, based on existing strategic EU documents (New Battery Regulation and the Data Governance Act) and aiming for maximum interoperability in the context of reverse logistics. In this process we will follow the agile standardisation approach for data models specification. The outcome of the above work will be published in the D2.2 Prototype of the battery data model.

2.4. Increase data Re-use

The documentation and explanation that ease understanding and reusing data inside or outside the project is the responsibility of the partner that generates the data. The used format shall be explicit, and as far as possible rely on widely used domain standard and formats. The provider is also in charge of the quality of the data it generates.

Knowledge outputs will remain available for at least five years after project finalisation. Any public datasets will be stored and will be able to be handled in open formats (e.g., Open Office) using SI units, and providing relevant descriptions and metadata to ensure reproducibility.

Long term storage strategy is not defined yet and will be detailed in future version of the DMP.

3. Other research outputs

Other research output (like software, workflows, etc.) are also identified and tracked in the dataset inventory table.

4. Allocation of resources

Any data generated in BatteReverse is stored and managed under the responsibility of the data lead provider, with its own data management IT resources. Each partner will be responsible for quality assurance of the generated data and metadata.

During the project, each partner can rely on the collaborative platform provided by CEA to store generated data whenever it complies with the technical needs for data sharing and reuse among the project participants.

The cost related to long term storage strategy is not defined yet and will be detailed in future version of the DMP.

5. Data security

The project collaborative repository provides an individual secured access. Most of project data will be stored on this platform and kept open several months after the end of the project until long term preservation action are in place.

6. Ethics

BatteReverse does not collect personal data. The project does not anticipate any ethical issues at this point.

7. Other issues

Not relevant for BatteReverse